

Project CHANGES - Spoke 5

D. 3.5 Monitoring Dashboard

V1.0

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Executive Summary

The adoption of the Internet of Things (IoT) is transforming cultural heritage preservation by enabling real-time monitoring of environmental conditions. IoT-based systems collect data on temperature, humidity, light exposure, air quality, and vibrations, which impact the conservation of artifacts and historical sites. IoT dashboards are key in aggregating, visualizing, and analyzing these data, aiding conservationists and heritage managers in decision-making. They offer real-time visualization through time-series charts, heatmaps, spatial distribution maps, and automated alerts when critical thresholds are exceeded. Additionally, historical data analysis supports trend identification and correlation studies between environmental factors. This deliverable presents the state of the art in IoT dashboards, the developed methodology, and the results of applying these systems to monitor environmental conditions in cultural heritage contexts.

Introduction

Adopting digital technologies, particularly the Internet of Things (IoT), is increasingly beneficial for preserving cultural heritage sites. IoT-based monitoring systems enable real-time data collection on environmental parameters that impact the conservation of artifacts, buildings, and archaeological sites. IoT dashboards are crucial in aggregating, visualizing, and analyzing these data to support conservationists' and heritage managers' decision-making processes.

IoT dashboards serve as the primary interface for stakeholders to interact with monitoring systems, offering real-time data visualization through time-series charts, heatmaps, and spatial distribution maps. They provide automated alerts and notifications when predefined thresholds are exceeded, such as detecting excessive humidity that could lead to mold formation. Additionally, they support historical data analysis, enabling trend identification and correlation studies between different environmental variables. User access control ensures role-based permissions and customizable configurations.

IoT systems for cultural heritage monitoring typically consist of the following components: Sensor networks deployed across heritage sites collect data on temperature, humidity, light exposure, air quality, pollutants, and vibrations; Communication protocols to send real-time data with minimal energy consumption; and Cloud computing and edge computing to process data either locally through edge computing devices or transmitted to cloud platforms for storage and analysis.

This deliverable presents an overview of the state of the art in IoT dashboards, the methodology developed, and the results for monitoring environmental conditions in cultural heritage contexts.

1. State of art

Numerous scientific efforts have been made to protect cultural heritage (CH) through IoT, machine learning, and structural health monitoring (SHM) techniques, often supported by advanced dashboards for data visualization and decision-making. In Laborda et al., a wireless sensor network monitored environmental conditions at The Cloisters in New York, collecting data on temperature, humidity, air quality, and visitor impact. The dashboard-enabled system allowed experts to analyze trends and assess the long-term effects of air conditioning on artifacts. Similarly, Maksimovic et al. developed a three-level IoT architecture for the Church of the Holy Archangels in Sarajevo, integrating machine learning models like Decision Trees and Support Vector Machines. The system's dashboard facilitated real-time monitoring and automated decision-making for preventive conservation.

Dashboards play a crucial role in SHM applications, as demonstrated by Lorenzoni et al., where an advanced monitoring system for the Verona Arena was used to analyze structural stability. The system visualized SHM data to reduce uncertainties and optimize static and dynamic monitoring parameters. Bezas et al. used predictive modeling and machine learning techniques to anticipate damage in historic buildings, with dashboards enabling real-time risk assessment and intervention planning. Similarly, Trigona et al. described a museum monitoring system utilizing Bluetooth beacons and neural networks to reconstruct visitor trajectories, allowing dashboards to optimize space management and conservation strategies.

In microclimate monitoring, dashboards facilitate real-time data interpretation, as in Mitro et al., where Smart Tags connected through IoT middleware efficiently tracked environmental conditions near monuments. Meanwhile, Ribera et al. introduced a decision-support model for assessing historic buildings' Highest and Best Use (HBU). The proposed Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) leveraged dashboards to visualize financial, social, and cultural data, aiding stakeholders in making informed preservation decisions.

Machine learning models like decision trees are also integrated into dashboards to classify CH assets based on environmental risks. In Wang et al., decision trees were employed to identify the most vulnerable artifacts in museums and archaeological sites, with dashboards providing interactive visualizations of protection priorities. Additionally, autoencoders (AEs) are widely used for defect detection, as demonstrated in Liu et al., where a convolutional AE processed thermal images to identify potential damage to contemporary artworks. Dashboards in these systems offer intuitive interfaces for tracking degradation patterns and recommending restoration actions.

A significant advancement in dashboard-driven CH monitoring is the AeKNN model proposed by Garouani et al., which integrates autoencoders for latent feature extraction with kNN for classification. Unlike traditional approaches, AeKNN enhances dashboards by offering detailed reconstructions of deterioration patterns and early damage detection insights. This integration improves the accuracy and adaptability of CH monitoring across diverse materials and environmental conditions. De Simone et al. and Shishido et al. highlight that the model supports data-driven conservation by providing real-time alerts, predictive maintenance recommendations, and interactive visual analytics, ultimately setting a new benchmark for CH preservation.

2. Methodology

The proposed architecture supports the representation of the physical system, where each component is mapped to its corresponding implementation technology. The system is designed to ensure efficient data collection, processing, and visualization, leveraging modern cloud-based and containerized solutions.

Sensor Network. The sensor network consists of various physical sensors deployed at the designated site. These sensors continuously monitor environmental and contextual parameters and autonomously transmit the collected data to the infrastructure via a 4G connection. The communication protocol utilized is MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport), which is lightweight and optimized for IoT applications, enabling efficient data transmission with minimal overhead.

To facilitate message brokering and ensure a scalable and robust communication pipeline, the system integrates EMQX, a high-performance, distributed MQTT broker. EMQX manages multi-node communication between sensors and the rest of the system, implementing the publish-subscribe protocol to ensure efficient and reliable data distribution across all subscribing components. The use of EMQX enhances scalability by supporting concurrent message exchanges across a large number of nodes.

First sensor board (approximately 25 cm x 30 cm in size). Currently, the device only detects data without transmitting or storing them.

In the developed prototype in Figure 1, we created a platform with different IoT sensors. In detail, the sensor represents the first prototype assembly that was made specifically for the Misericordia church, and includes:

- **Raspberry Pi 4B:** A powerful single-board computer serving as the central data acquisition and sensor management processing unit.
- **HAT Brick:** An extension board that provides additional I/O interfaces for seamless integration with other sensor modules.
- **IMU Bricklet:** An inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensor capable of detecting motion, acceleration, and orientation changes.
- **Particulate Matter Sensor:** Measures the concentration of fine particulate matter (PM1.0, PM2.5, and PM10) in the air, crucial for air quality monitoring.
- **Air Quality Sensor:** Detects various air pollutants such as volatile organic

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compounds (VOCs), providing insights into environmental conditions.

- **Sound Pressure Sensor:** Captures sound levels in decibels (dB), applicable for noise pollution monitoring in urban environments.
- **CO2 Sensor:** Measures carbon dioxide concentration, which is critical for indoor air quality and environmental health assessments.
- **Ambient Light Sensor:** Monitors light intensity levels, which can be used for energy-efficient lighting control and environmental monitoring.
- **Libelium Smart Spot:** A multi-sensor device that integrates various environmental sensors for comprehensive urban monitoring.
- **Viti RPi Kit:** A specialized Raspberry Pi-based vineyard and agricultural monitoring kit, including temperature and humidity sensors.
- **4G Modem:** Enables cellular network connectivity, allowing real-time data transmission from remote sensor nodes.
- **SIM Data Card:** Provides mobile network access for IoT devices, ensuring uninterrupted data communication.
- **SD Card:** Used for data logging and system storage, ensuring sufficient space for temporary data retention before cloud transmission.
- **Monitor with Embedded PC:** A display system integrating processing capabilities, facilitating local data visualization and system control.

Data processing and Storage. Once the EMQX broker receives the sensor data into a time-series database for structured storage and retrieval, this process is facilitated by Telegraf, an open-source agent designed for collecting, processing, and forwarding metrics from various input sources to storage backends. Telegraf ensures that sensor data is preprocessed and transmitted to InfluxDB, a time-series database optimized for handling high-throughput, real-time data streams.

Deployment. The system is deployed within a cloud-hosted virtual environment to ensure scalability, availability, and ease of maintenance. The deployment stack includes:

- **Docker:** A containerization platform encapsulates system components into lightweight, portable, and isolated environments, ensuring modularity and seamless integration.
- **Virtual Private Server (VPS):** The application runs on a dedicated VPS to ensure optimal resource allocation and performance.

- **Ubuntu:** A stable and widely adopted Linux distribution used as the operating system for hosting the services.
- **Microsoft Azure:** The cloud infrastructure provider that offers computational resources, network scalability, and secure data management.

A separate **Apache HTTP Server** also hosts a 3D visualization interface that integrates geospatial data, allowing users to interact with mapped sensor locations and analyze real-time data streams.

2.2 Data Visualization and Analytics

The stored sensor data is visualized using **Grafana**, a powerful analytics and monitoring platform. Grafana enables real-time monitoring by querying InfluxDB and presenting sensor metrics in a structured and interactive dashboard. The figure illustrates various sensor readings, including:

- **Battery level trends:** Monitoring power availability to ensure the operational sustainability of sensors.
- **Environmental parameters:** Capturing temperature, humidity, and atmospheric conditions.
- **Data transmission rates:** Tracking the frequency and volume of messages the system receives to analyze network reliability.

The EMQX broker processes incoming messages at a frequency of **one message every 5-10 minutes per sensor**. As illustrated in the figure, the absence of dropped messages confirms the system's reliability and effectiveness in handling IoT data streams.

The application's dashboard provides an interactive showcase of Points of Interest (POIs), offering users an intuitive way to explore key locations. The system enables advanced analytics by integrating real-time sensor data, supporting data-driven decision-making for tourism flow monitoring and smart city applications.

The figure presents insights derived from multiple POIs, highlighting environmental conditions for specific aspects such as the temperature, humidity, air pressure, and air quality in real-time. These data are represented in a gauge format. In addition, historical data of a series of values related to temperature, humidity, and CO2 are presented in a graphical way to see their trend.

This figure provides a more specific dashboard related to air quality specification. Specific sensors installed in the location show real-time data related to PM (particulate matter) levels and acceleration data. These data are used for air Quality Monitoring. Indeed, high levels of PM (dust, pollutants, or soot) can degrade frescoes, paintings, sculptures, and delicate architectural elements. In addition, Monitoring PM levels helps

conservators take timely measures (e.g., adjusting ventilation, installing air filters, or restricting visitor access during high pollution periods). On the other side, acceleration supports the analysis of Structural Health Monitoring. In this case, acceleration sensors detect vibrations from environmental factors (traffic, construction) and human activity (visitor movement, events). This helps identify potential risks to structural integrity, such as resonance effects or micro-movements that could lead to cracks or long-term damage.

Finally, to enhance the preservation of historical sites, Monitoring sound levels is essential for protecting delicate architectural elements, frescoes, and historical artifacts. Excessive noise from large crowds can cause micro-vibrations that may accelerate structural wear and detach fragile decorations. A real-time dashboard tracking decibel levels can help conservators identify and mitigate acoustic stress, ensuring the church's long-term preservation. Similarly, illuminance monitoring helps prevent light-induced deterioration of paintings, textiles, and manuscripts. Excessive exposure to artificial lighting or direct sunlight can lead to fading, discoloration, and material degradation.

In general, it is possible to use these dashboards for the real-time monitoring of key parameters inside cultural heritage sites to prevent structural degradation, environmental damage, and safety hazards while enhancing visitor experience and operational efficiency.

2.3 Future Usage of these Data

While the current system successfully integrates IoT, cloud-based data management, and real-time visualization, several areas can be explored for further enhancements.

Specifically, integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques can enable more meaningful insights into the collected data. By applying AI-driven algorithms, the system can identify complex patterns, detect anomalies, and generate predictive models that anticipate variations in sensor readings.

For instance, AI models could analyze fluctuations in environmental conditions to predict changes in tourist flow patterns, air quality, or traffic congestion. Moreover, machine learning-based anomaly detection could automatically flag irregularities in sensor data, such as unexpected battery levels or inconsistent message transmission rates, improving system reliability and maintenance efficiency.

These enhancements will facilitate a more intelligent and autonomous decision-making process, supporting advanced applications in smart tourism, urban planning, and environmental monitoring.

Conclusions

The proposed system integrates IoT-enabled data acquisition, cloud-based storage, and advanced visualization techniques to enable real-time monitoring and decision support for cultural heritage sites. The use of containerized deployment (Docker), cloud-based hosting (Azure), and time-series data management (InfluxDB) ensures scalability, flexibility, and robustness.

We plan to include AI-driven predictive analytics and real-time anomaly detection to optimize experts' decisions in the following steps.

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